

**TACTICAL PARTICULARS REGARDING THE CONDUCT OF
CRIMINAL PROSECUTION AT THE INITIAL AND SUBSEQUENT
STAGE OF THE INVESTIGATION OF CORRUPTION CRIMES**

**PARTICULARITĂȚI TACTICE PRIVIND EFECTUAREA
ACȚIUNILOR DE URMĂRIRE PENALĂ LA ETAPA INIȚIALĂ ȘI
ULTERIOARĂ A CERCETĂRII INFRAȚIUNILOR DE CORUPȚIE**

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Summary: *In the last period of time, depending on the economic and socio-political situation in the country, we observe a constant persistence, an active spread of acts of corruption and the consolidation of their roots in all areas of social life. Under these conditions, corruption registers a weight that threatens the security of the state, the proper functioning of public power, the rule of law, democracy, human rights and social equity.*

Currently, new ways of committing acts of corruption appear, and the process of investigating them is usually accompanied by active resistance from the criminals and the people who have connections with them. It is also necessary to highlight the large number of errors committed by criminal prosecution bodies, admitted in the process of investigating corruption crimes (in particular, when carrying out criminal prosecution actions) that generate negative consequences in the field of preventing and combating acts of corruption and the consequences caused by these. In such circumstances, a continuous research and improvement of the tactics of carrying out criminal prosecution actions in the case of corruption crimes is necessary based on recommendations approved by forensic science.

Keywords: *crime, corruption, criminal investigation actions, criminal investigation body, criminal investigation situation, apprehension, blatant, evidence, evidentiary procedures, surveillance, special investigative measures, interception, recording, planning, active subject, tactics.*

Rezumat: *În ultima perioadă de timp, în dependență de situația economică și social politică din țară, observăm o persistență constantă, o răspândire activă a actelor de corupție și consolidarea înrădăcinării lor în toate domeniile vieții sociale. În aceste condiții, corupția înregistrează o pondere care amenință securitatea statului, funcționarea corespunzătoare a puterii publice, supremația legii, democrația, drepturile omului și echitatea socială.*

Actualmente, apar noi modalități de comitere a actelor de corupție, iar procesul de investigare a acestora este însoțit, de regulă, de o rezistență activă din partea infractorilor și a persoanelor care au legături cu ei. Este necesar să evidențiem și numărul mare de erori comise de organele de urmărire penală, admise în procesul cercetării infracțiunilor de corupție (în special, la efectuarea acțiunilor de urmărire penală) care generează consecințe negative pe tărâmul prevenirii și combaterii actelor de corupție și a consecințelor provocate de acestea. În asemenea circumstanțe, este necesară o cercetare și perfecționare continuă a tacticii efectuării acțiunilor de urmărire penală în cazul infracțiunilor de corupție în baza unor recomandări aprobate de știința criminalistică.

Cuvinte-cheie: *infracțiune, corupție, acțiuni de urmărire penală, organ de urmărire penală, situație de urmărire penală, reținere, flagrant, probe, procedee probatorii, supraveghere, măsuri speciale de investigații, interceptare, înregistrare, planificare, subiect activ, tactică.*

Criminal cases regarding acts of corruption are started immediately after becoming aware of the data containing convincing information about corruption, if, however, sufficient primary information is not available, the start of these cases will be preceded by the verification of the materials available to the bodies of criminal prosecution, verification carried out only for the purpose of establishing the legal grounds for starting such a criminal case. The verification must be done cautiously and secretly, because the guilty persons, hearing about the verification, may hide or destroy the compromising objects and materials, collude with the interested persons to give false testimony, etc. During the verification, the materials that are still needed will be obtained (data from forensic records will be requested, concrete documents will be studied, facts that explain and contain primary data, explanations will be obtained from official persons and some citizens, and will become familiar with the service activity of some officials or subdivisions). If the additionally obtained data will confirm the primary information, the criminal investigation body can start the criminal investigation and start the investigations (Gheorghiuță, p. 367).

The data regarding the nature of the act, the circumstances of its commission, the number of participants, the mode of operation and others, resulting from the verifications undertaken, make it possible to establish the necessary forces that will act in order to detect the flagrant crime (Petre, *et.al.*, p. 137).

The complexity and consecutiveness of the initial criminal prosecution actions are determined by the existing criminal prosecution situations at the time of the investigation of the corruption offences. In the situation where we have substantiated information about the commission of acts of corruption, which came from the corruptor or from other legal bodies, the following initial criminal investigation actions are usually carried out: 1) hearing witnesses and the whistleblower; 2) collection and research of documents that refer to the service

activity of the corrupt person; 3) searches at the place of residence and work; 4) investigation of the object of the act of corruption; 5) questioning the suspects; 6) presentation of the object (objects) for recognition, etc. Consecutiveness of carrying out these criminal investigation actions is usually the one referred to above. At the same time, depending on the circumstances of the case, it can be modified (Яблоков, pp. 605-606).

In the case of the second initial situation - when there are complaints from certain concrete persons regarding the extortion and transfer of money, goods, etc. – the following initial criminal prosecution actions are carried out: 1) hearing the declarant; 2) apprehension of the perpetrator in the act; 3) searches at the perpetrator's place of residence and work; 4) body search of the detained person, and in case of necessity - physical examination of him; 5) investigation of the objects of acts of corruption and investigation at the scene of the crime; 6) questioning the suspect; 7) hearing witnesses.

The consistency of criminal prosecution actions in this situation depends, to a large extent, on the results of the apprehension of the perpetrator in the act. Usually, after the arrest, a body search takes place, the investigation of the crime scene and the object of the corruption crime, the hearing of the suspect, witnesses, etc. Also, at the initial stage, in the case of both criminal investigation situations, certain categories of judicial expertise can be ordered and carried out.

In the case of the third initial situation (when the information about acts of corruption is obtained in the process of investigating other criminal cases), the complex of initial criminal prosecution actions is usually determined, as in the case of the first initial criminal prosecution situation (Яблоков, p. 606).

The investigation begins with *the hearing of the whistleblower*. This quality can be both the person from whom certain material goods and services are extorted, or who has already transmitted or offered them, as well as the person to whom they are proposed (pretended to buy). Such an act can take place both directly, between two people (the corruptor and the corrupt), and through an intermediary (Gheorghîță, p. 367).

The way in which the detection of flagrant crime is carried out, the concrete activities that are undertaken to achieve the proposed goals differ from case to case. It is essential that the way the activity is carried out establishes the existence of the crime, guilt and flagrant state.

From the point of view of forensic tactics, as a rule, joint activities are carried out. The perception of the activity carried out by the perpetrator at the time of the intervention of the criminal prosecution body is likely to ensure the proof of the existence or non-existence of the crime and, if so, of the guilt of the perpetrator, as well as the flagrant state. For this, it is required that the ascertaining body observes and notes what specific activities were carried out at the time of its intervention, the persons who carried them out, those against whom

they were directed, as well as the persons who perceived them and who will be able to be identified and heard, to give accounts of the deed and the circumstances of its commission (Petre, *et.al.*, pp. 141-142).

The red-handed apprehension of the perpetrator in the case of corruption crimes is a complex action that allows obtaining important evidence, raising the material object of the crime and unmasking the culprit by exerting a strong psychological influence on him (Соколов, *et.al.*, pp. 37-38).

Detention in flagrant aims to establish the fact of the transfer of money, assets to the responsible person, the unmasking of the corrupt and the corrupt at the time of the transfer of money and assets, as well as the immediate removal of these objects. For this reason, the success of red-handed detention depends on the correct assessment of the particularities of the place and time of the transfer of money and goods, their qualities, and the methods of fixing acts of corruption. It is also important that the detention is carried out in such a way that the corrupt person cannot get rid of the money or objects received until the detention and does not have time to invent and invoke certain arguments regarding their possession on him (Яблоков, p. 607).

Hearing at the place of detention, if the right conditions exist, is quite effective for several reasons. First of all, in front of the suspect are the circumstances of the crime scene and the material object of the act of corruption. Secondly, this state of affairs does not allow the corrupt person to materialize in his consciousness "a picture of rehabilitation" in order to invoke it before the criminal investigation body, exerting a substantial psychological influence on the person interviewed (Соколов, *et.al.*, p. 40).

When there are solid indications regarding the commission of a corruption crime, for the purpose of gathering evidence or to identify the perpetrator, the following measures may be ordered: 1) putting bank accounts and accounts assimilated to them under surveillance; 2) putting the suspects under operational surveillance and/or intercepting their communications in real time; 3) accessing computer systems used by suspects or their accomplices.

At the same time, it is possible to resort to undercover investigators, in order to collect data on the existence of the crime and to identify the persons who are suspected of having committed a crime, if the crime of corruption cannot be discovered or the perpetrators cannot be identified by other means (Stancu, p. 684).

In order to carry out the actual interception and recording operations, it is necessary that the criminal investigation bodies and specialized workers within the law enforcement agencies be made available to them the minimum necessary data. Such data allow the correct choice of concrete methods of action and technical means and may refer to the criminal activity, the personality of the perpetrators, the methods used by them, the place and time of the meetings that

are to be monitored, etc. (Petre, *et.al.*, p. 128).

Hearing witnesses. The accusation is usually based on a system of circumstantial evidence that represents an unbroken chain of facts pointing to the commission of the crime by a certain person. By virtue of this fact, when investigating corruption crimes, witness statements and the ability of the representative of the criminal investigation body to identify witnesses who could confirm certain facts related to the commission of acts of corruption, including indirect ones, are of substantial importance (Кушниренко, p. 81).

A large part of the witnesses in the case of corruption crimes becomes known from the materials that served as the basis for the initiation of the criminal prosecution, another category is established as a result of the special investigative activity, and the third – is established in the process of carrying out the initial actions of prosecution. They are identified, for the most part, from the category of persons trained in service relationships in connection with which the acts of corruption took place, persons informed about the service activity of persons with a position of responsibility (acquaintances, friends, relatives, etc.), as well as from people who have certain relations with corrupt persons (corruptor and corrupt) (Яблоков, p. 606).

Determining the tactical scheme for hearing witnesses in the case of acts of corruption depends on the following factors: 1) the attitude of the person being heard towards the investigated deed (the leader or subordinate of the corrupt person is, directly or indirectly, related to the investigated acts); 2) the consequences that may occur for the witness in case he makes truthful statements; 3) the amount of information the witness has; 4) the presence of family relationships with the corrupt person; 5) exerting influence on the witness in order to determine him to conceal certain information (Соколов, *et.al.*, pp. 40-41).

In corruption offences, the hearing of these persons is, of course, mandatory. This activity will be subject to the following tactical rules: knowing the people to be listened to; drawing up the listening plan and other preliminary activities; establishing the place where the hearing, summoning and bringing of the persons will take place, the time when it will be carried out.

The hearing will be conducted, first of all, according to the known tactical rules, depending on the stages that the hearing goes through. Especially in the phase of asking questions, it is necessary to insist on elucidating the concrete circumstances in which the money, goods (uses) were received, where they were placed (hidden), other concrete aspects that can prove the facts and that can be constituted as evidence or means trial. It will be clarified how he met the perpetrator, established relationships, his interest, possible previous agreements (if any) regarding the place and time when they were to meet, the amounts of money (goods) he had to give, the characteristics, their provenance and

justification. The perpetrator's claims after committing the act and his position will be recorded (Stancu, pp. 694-695).

The series of issues to be clarified in the process of hearing witnesses and the tactics of carrying out this criminal prosecution action depends on their level of information and their relations with the subjects of corruption crimes (Кушниренко, p. 82).

Hearing witnesses usually allows us to learn about the contacts of participants in corruption crimes, about the behavior of the person in charge, about the extortion of money, goods, services, etc. In the process of hearing the people from whom money, goods, services are extorted, it is necessary to clarify who is the person who claims them, for what exactly they are to be transmitted, whether they are intermediaries or not, under what circumstances the goods, money are to be transmitted (Яблоков, pp. 606-607).

In general, the circle of witnesses in corruption crimes must be widened to the maximum both through the follow-up actions carried out and with the help of operative-investigative methods and means (Драпкин, *et.al.*, p. 596).

The on-site investigation in the case of corruption offenses aims to specify, clarify the circumstances, the circumstances in which the acts were committed. The basic task of this criminal prosecution action is to establish traces of the presence of the subjects of corruption crimes at the place where the act was committed, the discovery of the objects of the acts of corruption or some of their fragments, envelopes, packaging materials, etc. (Соколов, *et. al.*, p. 38). In the process of carrying them out, they can be discovered, fixed and raised traces of the transmission, receipt of money, goods, including documents to be investigated separately (Яблоков, p. 608).

The general issues that must be clarified by the investigation of the place of the act of corruption are grafted on the constitutive elements of the acts of corruption, these being the following: 1) the identity, quality and participation of the persons in the commission of the acts of corruption; 2) the illegal actions and inactions of these persons, including those related to their duties; 3) the purpose of criminal activities; 4) the money or benefits that constitute the object of the criminal activity (Petre, *et.al.*, p. 149).

The process of investigating the scene of the crime requires special physical and mental efforts, constituting an activity that requires those who perform it to maintain, for long periods of time, an intense mental concentration. On the other hand, its improper implementation can lead to the omission of evidence and compromise the results.

Achieving the objectives of a crime scene investigation requires the use of imagination, spontaneity and capitalizing on the experience gained in this field, and the interpretation of traces and the gradual elaboration of the versions constitute a continuous process that advances parallel to the actual conduct of the

investigation.

The delimitation of the crime scene is purely conventional, the area of research can be gradually expanded depending on the results obtained previously. Therefore, it is possible that the claim is consumed in one place, and the receipt of money or other benefits in another place, or that the money is received or even claimed through one or more intermediaries, complicit in the commission of crimes (Petre, *et.al.*, pp. 145-146).

In the course of the investigation, documents, values and other means of evidence will be sought from which aspects related to the facts themselves, but which contribute to the resolution of the criminal case, will be found: the work duties of the perpetrator, relations with the informant, goods or values likely to be the subject of the insurance measures, the sums of money or other benefits that could come from the commission of other acts of corruption (goods that exceed the real needs of consumption or use, the multitude of goods of the same kind and with the same characteristics, etc.).

A separate category of traces that, in the procedure for establishing flagrant corruption crimes, have a particular relevance is the traces of fluorescent substances. Moreover, in such a situation, the investigation of the crime scene is closely related to the activities preceding and simultaneous to the detection of flagrant crimes. It is also necessary to describe the object that carries them and that can possibly be lifted to be photographed under laboratory conditions (Petre, *et.al.*, p. 147).

In the process of *researching documents* in the case of corruption crimes, we can discover facts that confirm the correctness or incorrectness of the actions carried out in the interest of the corruptor, as well as data that inform us about the amount of money or the value of the goods transferred (Яблоков, p. 608). Also, when researching the documents, more attention should be paid to those documents that contain information or tell us about: 1) the illegality of the actions (inactions) of the persons with the responsibility function; 2) the simplified procedure for making certain decisions or decisions, the illegal route taken by documents through the secretariat, chancellery; 3) falsification of documents; 4) the amount of assets and values related to the commission of acts of corruption; 5) the circumstances that create conditions for extortion or bribery determine the commission of acts of corruption (Соколов, *et.al.*, pp. 38-39).

One of the most important initial prosecution actions in the case of corruption offenses is *the search*. For this category of crimes, group searches are often carried out at the workplace and living quarters of several subjects of corruption acts. Delaying the search may result in the irretrievable loss of important evidence. However, it is necessary to establish the specific time of the search in order to exclude resistance from the corrupt and the transmission of important information and messages to co-participants (Драпкин, *et.al.*, p. 597).

In order to carry out this criminal prosecution action, substantial criminal procedural and tactical-criminological preparations are necessary. Procedural preparations involve ensuring compliance with the regulatory framework when conducting the search. Also, during the tactical training period, the criminal investigation body is to analyze all the evidence accumulated up to this point and the information obtained as a result of the special investigative activity. The volume and duration of preparatory activities depends on the time available to the prosecuting body in this regard (Кушниренко, p. 83).

In the case of searches in corruption cases, it is important to know exactly the people who, legally, live in these rooms, whether or not they share some spaces (to legalize the search), what communication paths with the outside are, especially doors, disguised windows, etc.; in the case of some offices, their disposition in relation to other functions, the detection of those where the official still has access by virtue of the legalities of the service, possibly the places where he keeps his wardrobe, wardrobe, changing room, etc.

Considering the quality of the active subject of corruption crimes, it is good for the judicial body to take into account the information that is known about the personality of the person to be searched.

Also, the team tasked with carrying out the search will consist of a sufficient number of people who will be assigned tasks. The team must prepare the technical means that will be used to find the money, objects, documents or other evidence. Each team member will act according to previously established tasks. Naturally, a body search must be carried out from the beginning. It is also advisable to carry out the search of cars or other vehicles, with the participation of an expert in the matter (Stancu, pp. 696-697).

The body search of the detained persons is carried out, first of all, to discover the objects of the crime of corruption. More than that, in the process of the body search, documents, assets, documents can be discovered that also tell us about the commission of other acts of corruption (Соколов, *et.al.*, p. 38). It is also necessary to pick up, or at least study, the diaries, correspondence, notebooks, registers, audio-video recordings, computers, often these being carriers of very important evidence (Stancu, p. 697).

The tactics of carrying out the search depends on the nature of the objects sought, which can be: goods or money-objects of acts of corruption, their fragments, the documents of provenance of the goods (passports, technical characteristics, instructions, etc.), documents, diaries, correspondence, documents that talk about the way of life of the searched person (sales-purchase contracts, titles of ownership of movable and immovable property, technical passports of means of transport, etc.), electronic carriers of information that are important for research (computers, mobile phones, electronic diaries, etc.), photos, audio-video recordings, documents that highlight the personal and work

relationships of the person searched with other people, jewelry, etc. So, the characteristics of the searched objects predetermine the tactics of conducting the search (Крюков, pp.12-13).

The tasks of the search at the place of work or living are not limited only to the discovery of objects of corruption offences. They are much wider. In particular, during the search, we are going to draw attention to various documents, to correspondence with other people, to telephone numbers, addresses that tell us that the participants in the acts of corruption are known, or that there is an understanding between them regarding the commission of the crime. It is necessary to remember the following moment; in the case of corruption offences, the measure of special confiscation can also be applied. Accordingly, in the search process it is necessary to discover certain assets in this regard and to place them under seizure (Яблоков, p. 608).

The particularities of searching corrupt persons are attributed to: 1) the difficulty of discovering the bodies of crimes and other evidence, because they are carefully hidden; 2) the need for a proper assessment of all discovered objects, documents and records, as they may also be encrypted; 3) the possibility of using the help of the corruptor or the intermediary who provides verified statements (Соколов, et.al., pp. 39-40).

During the subsequent stage of the investigation, witness hearings are most often conducted (we mean new witnesses and those previously heard, in whose statements ambiguities, uncertainties or distortions crept in), certain categories of expertise are arranged and conducted in courts, the hearing of persons accused of committing corruption offenses is carried out (Яблоков, pp. 608-609).

At the later stage of the investigation of corruption crimes, one of the most complex criminal prosecution actions is the hearing of the accused. This is due either to the lack of direct witnesses to acts of corruption, or to the lack of interest of all participants in discovering their own criminal activity. Also, all participants in corruption crimes, if they are brought to criminal responsibility, try hard to evade, interpret the act of corruption as a return of the debt, and the money or objects received - as being found or forgotten by someone (Яблоков, pp. 609-610).

Given the particularities of committing corruption crimes, *the hearing of the suspect, the accused* must be carefully prepared, considering the prospect of a psychological dispute between the criminal investigation body and the criminal in order to establish the truth, the existence or not of the criminal act.

For the smooth progress of the research, it is necessary to carefully study all the materials, the data held in the case. Thus, it is of interest: the way of reporting to the judicial body, the concrete circumstances and the way in which the act was committed, if the perpetrator was caught red-handed or through direct investigation. The author must give explanations about the values that were the

object of the corruption, if they were found on him, where in what quantities or amounts, what other evidence exists in the file. Depending on the particularities of each corruption case, its complexity, the extent of the criminal activity, the hearing covers, broadly speaking, the following: workplace and duties, the circumstances in which he met the person from whom he claimed and received money or other benefits, the place, time, conditions in which he received the money, goods and purpose.

It is important to determine what he had to do in exchange for them, whether they were legal or not. It must also be determined what he did with the sums of money and goods and what was their destination. It must also be determined if he has committed other acts and if anyone else knows about them (Stancu, pp. 691-610).

The tactical peculiarities of hearing the suspect, the accused, are determined by the personal characteristics of the corrupt person, as well as by the specifics of the investigation of acts of corruption, which consists in the lack of direct evidence and of well-informed persons, interested in establishing the truth. By virtue of this fact, the importance of hearing the suspects, the accused, is enormous. First of all, their statements can become a source of information regarding the committed act, which can contribute to the submission of versions on each element of the evidence object. Or, the information obtained in the hearing process contributes to the identification of ways to search and verify the collected evidence. Secondly, in the hearing process, the position of the subject of the crime against the committed deed is clarified, the defense versions of the perpetrator can be predicted. And, finally, thirdly, during the hearing, the criminal prosecution body performs the psychological diagnosis of the criminal in order to select the most effective and correct tactical procedures for carrying out criminal prosecution actions (Кушниренко, pp. 75-76).

The hearing of suspects, accused in the case of corruption crimes often takes place in conflict situations characterized by insufficient evidence. Taking advantage of the fact that the transfer of money and goods takes place most often in the absence of suspected witnesses, the accused deny any contacts with the corrupt person. If the latter admits the transfer of the assets, he is to questioned thoroughly not only about the circumstances of committing the crime, but also about the events preceding or following the corruption (Драпкин, *et.al.*, pp. 597-598).

The assessment by the criminal investigation body of the psychological state of the suspect, the accused, has a special role. As a rule, confidence in their own innocence, contemptuous attitude towards the criminal investigation body, and knowledge of their rights is typical for them. At the same time, the suspect, the accused may be dominated by fear, anxiety regarding the uncertainty of his position, fear of the possible measure of procedural-criminal coercion, the

impossibility to foresee the consequences of the created situation and to orient himself properly in these circumstances, the lack of knowledge of the evidence at hand the disposition of the criminal prosecution body. Namely, this psychological state of the suspect, the accused, must be the basis for the development and application of tactical-psychological hearing procedures: penetration into the plans and intentions of the perpetrator, the transmission of indirect information, the use of contradictions between co-participating perpetrators, etc. (Крюков, p. 12).

In the process of preparing for the hearing of the accused in the case of corruption crimes, it is of particular importance to study the person of the person being heard, to detect some character traits and particularities that would facilitate the selection of certain tactical hearing procedures. Also, we should have a clear vision on the tactics of presenting certain evidence to the accused (presentation of confessional testimonies of the corruptor, of the intermediary, extracted from the bank accounts of the accused, use of operative-investigative information, etc.). All these procedures can create the impression of detailed information of the criminal investigation body on the circumstances of the case.

When questioning the accused, it is also rational to detail the answers obtained as much as possible regarding the circumstances of the crime committed. However, this would prevent their subsequent attempt to recant the statements they made. For the same purpose, in the process of questioning the suspect, it is recommended to apply audio-video recording (Яблоков, pp. 609-610).

Or, depending on the ways of committing corruption crimes, as well as the specific circumstances that preceded, accompanied and succeeded the criminal activity, the hearing of the suspect, the accused aims to clarify the essential aspects for establishing all the circumstances in which the act was committed and the guilt (Stancu, p. 692).

In the case of several persons suspected, accused of committing corruption crimes, it is recommended to hear, first of all, the persons predisposed to give truthful statements. Thus, in the line of corrupters we can identify people who acted under the influence of fraudsters, blackmailers, who previously expressed themselves about committing acts of corruption. Among the intermediaries and the corrupt, the persons trained in criminal activity through blackmail will be heard, first of all, those who are dissatisfied with their subordination and their status within the criminal group, with the method of distribution of the means obtained by committing acts of corruption or those who, in generally, negatively assesses his participation in the criminal group (Драпкин, p. 599).

Due to the particularities of these crimes and, above all, the "consensual" nature of the acts committed by the participants, the investigations, in general, the criminal prosecution will be difficult, having to resort to confrontations

between the participants, including those with witnesses or whistleblowers.

The contradictions concern the aspects related to the realization of the claim of certain sums of money or other values, to the conduct of the official who accepted or did not reject those offered.

In each case, the appropriateness of the confrontation must be assessed. It is important to take into account, beyond the general tactical aspects, the psychosocial impact, the possibility of exerting pressure on the parties, witnesses, but also the alternative of an attempt to compromise or revenge. After studying the file, in order to identify the contradictions and their causes, the persons to be confronted will be determined. They will be listened to first to see if they stand by their previous statements, if they are honest or if they fear confrontation.

Carrying out the actual confrontation involves clarifying those contradictions that concern the constitutive elements of the crime of corruption, especially those concerning the subject of the crime, the objective and subjective side of the act (Stancu, pp. 695-696).

Disposition of judicial expertise and technical-scientific findings. In the investigation of corruption crimes, given the specificity of these facts, the most frequently ordered or approved are the graphoscopic ones, the technical expertise of the documents, photography, the identification of the person by voice and speech, technique, of coins and banknotes, of works of art, financial- accounting etc. Of course, dactyloscopic, traceological, biological, etc. expertises should not be excluded either.

In the last period of time, recordings intended to document acts of corruption have become frequent and legal, in particular, the interception of communications through audio and video systems. From here, naturally, we arrived at the voice and speech expertise requests, intended to identify a person, through this means of evidence, to establish the authenticity and legality of a recording, but also of possible counterfeiting.

The usefulness of this kind of expertise, in corruption crimes, is obvious, given that they are committed in confidential, even sophisticated forms and ways, the perpetrators, not only the well-versed, taking special precautions.

Regarding the other judicial expertise, not only forensic, it is obvious that they will have as their object the clarification of some essential circumstances of corruption crimes, which really require the knowledge of an expert, not "collateral" issues, intended to delay the resolution of the case (Stancu, pp. 698-699).

Conclusions

The organization and tactics of conducting criminal prosecution actions in the process of investigating corruption crimes depend on the circumstances of the case, the criminal prosecution situations and many other objective and subjective

factors. The tactics of the initial prosecution actions in the process of investigating corruption crimes are determined depending on the possibility of applying the surprise effect, the presence or absence of eyewitnesses, and the specific situations of the investigation process of this category of crimes. The effectiveness of the investigation of corruption crimes is to be determined, first of all, by an accumulation of procedures and tactical means applied in the process of carrying out criminal prosecution actions at all stages of the investigation of criminal cases. Based on the fact that corruption crimes are attributed to the category of "self-documenting facts", it is necessary for the representatives of the criminal investigation bodies to know in detail the provisions of the normative acts that regulate the activity of persons with a position of responsibility, the organization chart and the structure of the organization in which the public person works, its rights, powers and obligations.

Also, from a tactical point of view, each criminal prosecution action carried out in the process of investigating acts of corruption has its own specifics, where an important role is also played by knowing the psychological aspects regarding their execution. At the same time, it is inadmissible to violate the provisions of the law, the ethical norms and the principles of the law, and the psychological influence must not turn into an illegal psychological violence, applied to the performance of criminal prosecution actions.

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